

PROJECT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SUSTAINABILITY OF PROJECTS FUNDED BY WORLD FOOD PROGRAM IN KENYA: CASE STUDY OF FEEDING PROGRAMS IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN KIBERA, NAIROBI

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Abstract: World Food Programme, feeding projects have been designed for various communities living in Kenya. Feeding programs in the slums were initiated to increase school attendance by providing food for learners in public schools. However, the sustainability of such programs remains a challenge. There were challenges with the continuity of the programme as the government is yet to release funds to cover the counties that previously benefited from the programme. The aim of this research was to explore the project management practices and sustainability of projects funded by the World food program in Nairobi County, Kibera constituency. The specific objectives were to determine how project management, stakeholder need assessment, cost management, quality management, and monitoring and evaluation management affect the sustainability of World Food Programme sponsored projects in Kenya. The survey was anchored on the theories of Change, Empowerment, and Institutional. A regression model was utilized to examine the effect of stakeholder's assessment, cost management, quality management and, monitoring and evaluation management on sustainability of projects under the study. Regression result shows that project management practices had a positive significant impact on the project sustainability of funded projects. The study concludes that the project management practices adopted have been effective in Kibera constituency. The study recommends that the organizations should pay keen attention to project cost management practices of the projects. Secondly, the study recommends that project quality management practices should be enhanced. Lastly, the study recommends that a monitoring committee should be established to review the projects on regular basis.

Keywords: World Food Programme, Feeding Projects, Project Monitoring and Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Project sustainability means the adaptability of tasks to maintain efficiency over a planned period Jennings, Browning & Rigolon [1] They want to start and launch profitable businesses after the input obligations have been wiped out Geneletti, La Rosa, Spyra, and Cortinovis [2] Business support work should be integrated into the time of the business plan

Linnenluecke et al. [3] Project sustainability varies in profitability, including framework credibility, continuous improvement of profits, fair allocation of profits from the company, dynamic community contribution and collaboration in tasks, and ongoing activities. It can be divided into indicators. The project design and consideration for nature incorporates solidity. History is shortly after the end of sponsorship and other aid, lack of funding, unfortunate support of tasks by the local environment, lack of sound organizational processes, or inadequacy of the company in the target population Elmqvist et al., [4,1]

During the twentieth century, the sustainable development concept was introduced. The first approval of the Sustainable Development approach was the 1972 Stockholm Convention, which concluded that humanity has acquired the ability to change the environment in various ways on an unprecedented scale. The Convention further emphasized that everyone is responsible for protecting the environment for both current and future generations. It also emphasized that social and economic development is of paramount importance in contributing to the quality and good living conditions of humankind.

Kim and Ronny [5] focus on Commission-funded study of dare to develop board skills, given the lack of a clear support scheme. Thus, they challenged the need to build manageability in federation structures rather than building federation structures.

Kim and Ronny [6] studied project management professional's role in enhancing manageability. The survey revealed that management role has the special skills and abilities expected of such a drive. It also emphasized that their significance is not limited to their utilitarian work, but to the broader organizational missions that allow them to achieve change. These activities include testing existing practices, suspicions, and procedures to ensure progress and awareness of task goals.

Kim and Ronny [7] noted that sustainability strategies require clear goals to ensure their implementation. Nevertheless, the unfortunate economic and political difficulties of most African countries impede governance in contrast to the rest of the masses. Earlier findings suggested a combination of legitimate preparatory parts, rational meaning of task goals, significant grants for the life of the project, and exercises to the concept of planned regulation.

In a previous study by Elmqvist et al, [4,2] challenges in managing development projects in South Africa included manager costs, lack of motivation from partners, time constraints, and lack of skills. Elmqvist et al. [4,3] also established that the principle of sustainability should be rehearsed throughout the life cycle of a company. More so, Morell, [7] documented that challenges involved emanated from planning, the project, stakeholders, material, and equipment related, and external constraints.

Mojtahedi, M., & Oo, B. L. [8] need to evaluate the regulations and policies associated with project management and sustainable projects to find impact on the challenges associated with leveraging the manageability of the project's board of directors. I thought there was. Her study of structural projects in South Africa found that the challenges of support were partners, funding, interactions, and board leadership. Various issues are information-related, partner-related, and cost-related.

In Africa, like other parts of world, sustainable improvement remains a test of many variables such as poverty, hunger, drought, illness, lack of education, health problems etc. Sub-Saharan Africa leads in countries with the highest levels of residents living in extreme poverty that is living on \$1.25 or less a day. For this reason, the non-governmental organization mobilized funds from a well-wisher to help eradicate hunger in African; they especially targeted schools in marginalized areas. In Nairobi, NGOs initiated a project to provide food for marginalized children in slums to help reduce the hunger effect on the student schooling processes.

Kibra constituency is one of the areas in Nairobi where the free feeding program was carried out before its recent suspension. Uncertainty is now rife with the program as the government is yet to release funds to ensure continuity. Learners who depended on the program risk drop out. With the exit of World Food Program funding in June 2018, the government had affirmed the sustainability of the project but the same is yet to be realized. Most schools depleted their reserves that were to run until April 2019 way at the beginning of the year. Historically, the international players had been heavily depended on to fund the feeding program since 1980, but the same had been crippled by frequent fluctuations in funding. To ensure sustainability, the Kenyan government had introduced homegrown feeding programs in the year 2009. This initiative was marred with financial constraints and several challenges.

1.1.1 Project Management Practices

Morell, [9] described project management practices as an action comprising of activity that creates an outcome, utilizing at least one strategy and method. The best practice is a demonstrated cycle that conveys quantifiable improvements in proficiency and viability. Organizations look for the accepted procedures to assist them with speeding up their advancement toward improving the performance and to direct them around the traps that could moderate or even end their initiatives.

Gabriela &Madalena [10] opined the need for organizations to enhance their project management practices in areas of stakeholder assessment, cost management, quality management, and monitoring and evaluation management to increase project performance. They further noted that project management practices vary relied on the project type, application area, and contextual factors thus organizations need to identify the best tools and techniques to be used in their projects. Stindt, [11] concluded by saying project management practices aim to enhance organizational value and ensure sustainability.

1.1.2 Sustainability of Projects

World Environmental Development Commission (WCED) noted that sustainability is a kind of advancement aimed at meeting present necessity while not interfering with the capability of those who meet future needs. This definition emphasizes future direction as an important factor in maintainability efforts. The International Institute for Sustainable Development 2010 is a technology that meets the ongoing needs of businesses and their accomplices while ensuring sustainability, security and improvement of human and ordinary assets to meet future demands. Project sustainability is about the connection of financial, ecological and social tasks, summarized as a 3-P concept.

Soma, DijkshoornDekker, and Polman [12] show, there are gaps in venture management degrees regarding the ability to integrate maintainability into the activity cycle. The author argues that these ideas play an important role in partnerships in terms of sustainability and that they need to be integrated into the ability to dare leaders. In relation to sustainability and project management Atlin and Gibson [13,1] indicates that pressure between different partners with the compromises required there needs to be investigated. Manageability is a prerequisite for maintainability of activities, regardless of marketable strategy or ability to accommodate different partners.

Project sustainability has been operated by some researchers in several ways, including frankness and responsibility von Wirth et al., [14] As per the Atlin and Gibson, [13,2] various clues can be used to measure manageability. They reduced overall functionality and improvement costs, increased the number of recipients, increased the degree of air and water quality, increased friendly interest, the ability to utilize nearby assets, and the overall progress of the project. The current study will measure sustainability by using Reduced Drop Out of school and improved performance innovative techniques such as kitchen gardening. Measuring sustainability encourages the participation of all key stakeholders in developing sustainable goals from the onset of a project. Sustainable projects must meet the social, economic, and environmental requirements.

1.1.3 Projects Funded by World Food Programme in Kibra Nairobi

The country strategic plan (CSP) 2018-2023 was launched by the World food programme (WFP) laying out its advancing movement from the provision of direct help to reinforce national systems and the ability to distribute food and nutrition security. Wide-ranging partner discussions assist in enhancing consensus on WFP's strategic direction, facilitating on country Zero Hunger Strategic Review.

World Food Program is a United Nation agency working to save and change lives by giving food assistance in areas of emergency, nutrition requires leading healthy lives as well as building resilience. It works with 83 countries around the world and assists millions of people in achieving food security and proper nutrition, therefore, reducing hunger. In Kenya, the world food program has supported various primary schools in different counties such as, Kibra constituency in which some public and needy private schools have been supported.

Their areas of operation include emergency interventions, relief and rehabilitation, developmental aid, and special operations. Most of their work is concentrated on the conflict-prone areas of the world as such areas are in dire need.

Since 2009, the programmes have taken the roles of dealing with school meals as credited by the Ministry of Education. WFP upheld the handover through a joint mission, training, and exchange of staff to enhance national capacity in data gathering, reporting, procurement, monitoring and evaluation, and management of programme. The Government

completely took over the obligation regarding giving school meals to children in primary school arid and semi-arid areas of Kenya in July 2018. Recently it pulled out its funding in the informal settlements in Nairobi and the program came to halt. The Ministry of Education is yet to continue the program in schools.

The Ministry of Education in Kenya formulates and implements policies that assist Kenyans access quality and affordable education. In conjunction with the World food programme, they have implemented school meal programmes targeting marginalized and informal settlements in Kenya. The aim was to increase enrolment rates and completion rates of students in such areas. In 2009, the local government started a public school care program to provide food for school children and improve the nearby economy.

To guarantee sustainability the WFP fortified the limit of the State Department for Social Protection to lead and facilitate the social protection sector, involving guaranteeing that the design improvements of the national social protection programmes food security needs. A generic management system was developed, tested, and approved by WFP to be utilized in all counties. The system is connected to the national single registry and will guarantee that social protection importance given by the county and national governments are represented for and information is managed proficiently and cost-effectively.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

World Food Programme permitted businesses to offer and provide food from locations other than where schools were located. They supply cooking oil, utensils, and other supplies for cooking. Currently, students provide their own dishes, and parents must contribute to the purchase of cooking supplies and the payment of chefs. World Food Programme projects have been designed for various communities living in Kenya. Nairobi slums have been the center of focus for many projects funded by world food programmes. The school meals programme has led reduction in the number of school drop-outs through curbing absenteeism, which in turn has led to improved performance.

Food security, according to Jack, [15] is dependent on ensuring that both rural and urban inhabitants can secure their livelihoods and so have access to the food they require through direct production, purchase, or barter. The problem of project sustainability has in Kibera constituency has alarming with many projects abandoned with spoiled. The vulnerabilities of such WFP projects include reliance on the cash economy, heavy spending on food and basic administration, various natural and health risks, inadequate housing and instability of housing, and illegality. Due to its openness to crime and malice, it varies from region to region (Atlin and Gibson. [13,3])

Atlin and Gibson [13,4] studied on how partner assessment practices are needed to influence the presentations of corporate associations. Observations have shown that partners with power, ownership, and credibility have shown viable management of the disaster. The finding also established that quality management, monitoring and evaluation, cost management affect the performance of these projects. Kamalirad, Kermanshachi, Shane and Anderson, [17] assessed the effect of primary stakeholder communication on complex projects. The survey established that the project characteristic enhance effective communication. Galas, PilatLeonardi, and Tobiasz-Adamczyk [18] assessed the pathway that projects have to follow to ensure that they function perfectly. The findings indicated that project management practice positively impacted the project sustainability. The survey by Batselier and Vanhoucke [19,1] studied the impact of monitoring and evaluation on private hospital projects. They established that community participation is critical in project sustainability since: it results in new knowledge that is more responsive to the needs of the main stakeholders.

Few studies have been conducted on the subjected matter with little done on project management practice on WFP projects. However, other studies have ignored variables such as cost and quality management practices which this study intends to fill. The studies were carried out in different organizations with none of the studies conducted in Kibera constituency. Therefore, this research seeks to look into influence project management practices affect the sustainability of world food programme funded projects in Kibra Constituency, Nairobi County.

1.3 Research Objective

1.3.1 General Objective

The general objective of the research was to explore how project management practices affect the sustainability of world food programme funded projects in Kibra Constituency, Nairobi County.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

The study was guided by the following specific objective

- i. To establish the effect of stakeholder needs assessment practices on the sustainability of world food programme funded projects in Kibra, Nairobi.
- ii. To investigate the effect of Project cost management practices on the sustainability of world food programme funded projects in Kibra, Nairobi.
- iii. To assess the effect of Project quality management practices on the sustainability of world food programme funded projects in Kibra, Nairobi.
- iv. To determine the effect of Project monitoring and evaluation management practices on the sustainability of world food programme funded projects in Kibra, Nairobi.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

According to Jones and Kierzkowski, [20,1] a theory is overall assumptions and principles utilized to depict a specific set of realities or some noticed phenomenon. Also, the theoretical framework comprises related thoughts that give direction to a research project or business endeavor. Freeman [21] demonstrates that a theory comprises ideas and causal connections that relate to these ideas. A theory can likewise be portrayed as an overall group of suppositions and principles used to depict a specific set of facts. This research adopts the theory of change, empowerment, and institutional theory considered relevant to the study.

2.1.1 Theory of Change

Jones and Kierzkowski [20,2] were the first proponent of the theory of change in the United States. It is a technology or tool utilized to plan, participate in, and evaluate projects development (not profit-oriented) to improve social change. It extensively depicts how and why the desired change is required to occur as Douthwaite and Hoffecker [22] puts it. The working principle of the theory is to determine long-term goals through reverse planning and linking results until the result structure is complete, and to determine the assumptions that lead to the establishment of indicators and the determination of intervention measures.

The theory of change is applicable in bringing maintainable advancement through quality control and cost the board. This is on the grounds that project implementers should strive to accomplish great outcomes by applying the ideas well in the undertaking cycle to concoct a superior educated speculation regarding change to help intercessions that can adjust to change in the unique situation Espiner. [23] Undertaking intercessions must be planned such that they carry long-term changes to that local area. The hypothesis of progress is significant in upgrading the supportability of tasks. Economical tasks are result based and this is what's really going on with the hypothesis of progress Luca. [24] Underscore ought to be on the use of the cycle and in long-term impacts.

The theory of change applies to sustainable progress through quality control and cost control. This is because project implementers must strive for great results by applying these ideas well in the engagement cycle, in order to fabricate advanced educational speculations on change, to aid intercession that can be adjusted in unique circumstances. Intercessions must be planned so that they can bring about long-term change in the region. The theory of change is of great importance to improve the compatibility of the task. Economic tasks are based on results, and this is the true meaning of the theory of change. The underline should be the use and long-term impact on the cycle.

The theory of change facilitates data collection and evaluation of projects. It enables the key participants to reveal what impacts and outcomes are expected and how exactly they are to be achieved. This further has an impact on project evaluation as it identifies what is to be measured, the interim and outcomes, the activities intended to achieve the outcome, and gives guidance on the options and choices to make on when and how to measure the changes.

However, its major limitations lie in its linearity concepts according to Allen [25,1] which assumes that inputs lead to outputs and this leads to outcomes. This might not be the case in some complex social phenomenon where linearity might not apply. Allana [25,2] also adduces that it risks promoting learning as the emphasis is made on complying with the donor rather than gaining knowledge from the entire process.

2.1.2 Empowerment Theory

The empowerment theory was proposed by Allana [25,3] The theory involves empowering people to achieve their goals by engaging with others. Control, participation and awareness are the building blocks of empowerment. Only when the idea of empowerment and its rational institutionalization in law, guidance process and governance mechanisms become a reality, will it be possible to achieve sustainable development Agner. [26]

Empowerment is a development that combines unique qualities and capacities, a common assistance framework and proactive practices in social arrangements and social changes Chen, Li & Li. [27] This theory combines individual prosperity with the larger political and social world. It is in this manner a purposeful progressing measure focused in the local community, involving mutual respect and participation of the group. Kang, Lee, and Kim [28] characterized it as a process through which individuals have powerful access and control over assets that do not have an equal share. Human beings thus gain control over their lives through democratic community participation Patton, [29] and a better understanding of their environment Logie, Lacombe-Duncan, Levermore& Jones,. [30]

Empowerment theories incorporate processes and results proposing that activities or constructions might be engaging and that the result of such process brings about a degree of being empowered Kral& Kidd. [31] Individuals can seek self-empowerment through processes such as participation in community-based projects. Decision-making and shared leadership are some of the tools that could be used to ensure empowerment at the organizational level. However, other empowering processes could incorporate collective activity to get to both government resources and the local community. The community empowerment level results may incorporate proof of pluralism, and the presence of organization alliances, and resources accessible to the community. Empowerment, therefore, entails people coming together to accomplish goals, group efforts to gain access to resources as well as better understandings of the sociopolitical environment. Empowering the community is therefore essential in fostering sustainability and analysis of stakeholder's needs assessments is therefore very important to understand their interest before embarking on a project.

2.1.3 Institutional Theory

Nelson Phillips conveyed that institutionalization is a cycle of institutional frameworks. This is the establishment of a manageable event transformation Lok. [32] The institution is the basic unit of every public sphere, and the way we shape human communication is almost the same as the way we make a blueprint for our daily lives. An organization can be seen as a set of well-defined practices and support structures that can enhance or enable the performance of an organization. It enables the attractive arrangement of exercises to be recognized as frequently as expected, and it is reiterated that these exercises flourish as principles van Wijk et al. [33] People stop doing things now because there are decisions, but because it is the norm Depoers and Jérôme. [34,1] Depoers and Jérôme [34,2] summarized this assumption: "A clear conclusion is that institutional development is the basic task to which they face NGOs because they continue to seek compatible event changes."

Wilmot, [35,1] defined Institutions as social routine programs. It consists of distinctive beliefs that affect organizational structure. Organizations that conform to the institution's norms are believed to be more efficient and effective. Within organizations, a set of standards and principles are developed to enable the realization of its goals. Organizations might change depending on internal and external happenings to survive. This forms part of the institutionalization process aimed at supporting the success and continuity of various ventures initiated.

The stability of institutions depends to a large extent on their suitability to the lifestyle and advantages of the subject and what it means for people Bouilloud, Pérezts, Viale and Schaepelynck. [36] The foundation considers the arrangements, practices and structures to handle a project. Proper and powerful fixes ensure consistency for future compatibility Wilmot, [35,2] believe that it is possible to formulate institutional laws through public evaluation or the use of important laws.

Recent work by Wilmot, [35,3] suggests that institutional theory is usually crippled by power and conflict. Max Weber whose work in sociology discerned that conflict, power, and interest are all inseparable further supports this. He further notes that bureaucracy is usually entrenched in institutions and serves some interest, and those whose interests are served become increasingly remote. He further affirms that institutions can become a source of alienation. This theory is significant to the current research because the management and operation of a project are coordinated by an organization. How efficiently the organization is will affect the sustainability of the project.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Li and Skitmore [37] focused on investigating how stakeholders influence green building assessments. They focused on what the supportable post-reconciliation activities mean for improving the project. This review was conducted in China and was attended by all partners of the association so as not to be overwhelmed by other development experts. This study used a quantitative approach to effectively demonstrate the impact of stakeholder participation in post-occupancy assessments. Stakeholders were categorized according to their influence and contribution. As a result, the survey found that the support of our partners had a decisive impact on the publication of development projects. The investigation found that the association's planning group was unable to further develop its structural plan due to lack of partner matching. This study shows how connectivity partners can directly drive a company's reputation in the long run. The main gap in the review was the failure to demonstrate the link between stakeholder impact and project sustainability, which was the focus of this review.

Di Maddaloni and Davis [38] focused on the impact of local individuals on megaprojects. A survey was conducted on a Canadian public foundation project. The review focused on tasks at the local area level. The results show that the stakeholder management helps real partners actually monitor and control project assets. The survey also showed that including a nearby assessment at the start of the project would increase project execution. The major gap from the study is that whereas it mainly focus on project performance which is mainly a short term objective. The current study goes beyond performance and analyze on project sustainability which is long term in nature as it aims at ensuring the continuity of the projects.

Kamalirad, Kermanshachi, Shane, and Anderson [17,2] evaluated how the response of key partners affects the outcome of complex activities. They focused on the contributions of key partners to builders and planners. The review categorized the variables and investigated the variables (internal correspondence) and their prevalence among developmentally dynamic individuals. The review summarized four research responses. The information test was guided by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Reviews have shown that project branding enhances communication success. The review envisioned some plans. The limits of financial strength to guarantee and the explanation of the framework of cooperation decisively characterize the internal response of major project partners. The major gap is that it focuses on communication which is one aspect of stakeholder involvement. The current study examined not just the stakeholder's involvement but also stakeholders' needs assessment.

Collings, Wood, and Szamosi, [39,1] evaluated the impact of resource design on the organizational performance. They utilized a descriptive research design during the survey. The survey recognizes that the manager decides the required assets, including different numbers of people, equipment and materials, which are sufficient to carry out actions, including functional information on the breakdown structure of work, access to recorded cost data related to tasks, scope explanation, description of the asset pool, and authorized arrangements are appropriate at this stage. Managers should identify risk defenses and objectives at this stage. By combining resources, managers will establish the collection of assets necessary to achieve their goals. The asset prerequisite that is, the top benefits at this stage - are critical to the different cost cycles of the board of directors. The main gap from the study is that it did not extensively focus on the cost management aspects of project management. Therefore, the current study focused on cost management aspects like project costs estimates and budgets.

Masaden,[40] assessed how ERP systems affect the process of project implementation. The study focused on group discussion to determine the ERP on resource planning project implementation. The survey recognized that in conclusion, the director need a period control schedule to avoid undue cost pressure. Schedule control helps determine the status of the committed schedule and handles actual changes when the schedule baseline occurs. The benefits of this phase, including review of quotes, spending updates, learning exercises, and gauges at fulfillment are key in cost the board. The main gap from the study is that it mainly examined cost management in relation to project implementation as opposed to project sustainability which is long term in nature.

Chatterjee [41,1] assessed how business domain capabilities, strategy, human capital investments, and project performance. This survey was done on the global software services industry. The survey used factor analysis to determine the effect of business domain capabilities factor, Strategy factor, and human capital investment factors on project performance. The survey found that funding challenges, inability of the board of directors, lack of management and involvement in development issues, and reckless arrangements are key variables that increase the number of projects bombed. There is a direct positive correlation between helpless plans and helpless on-site managers, which can promote expansion and plan

changes, leading to over-expansion of financial plans. As this study has shown, this model is very serious in underdeveloped countries and the implementation rate for some of these tasks reaches 100%. The basic factors that lead to this huge increase in expense include substandard materials. There is no principle to follow to guarantee the necessary materials for the task. Additionally, the inability of executives to stop spending due to incompetent spending is another major obstacle to project completion.

Chatterjee [41,2] did a research on the impact of total quality management on the sustainability of a project. The survey concentrated on the effect of TQM and the execution of management systems on the significance of a manager's place in performance. The study sampled 264 insurance firms in South African. The study used cross-sectional data to effectively explore the impact of TQM on performance. The study identified that managers use joint association when there is a degree in customers 'perspective. This reveals that customers' importance changes how the manager uses TQM. The study did not however focus on quality management practices like project frame wok and project policy which were the focus in the current study.

Chatterjee [41,3] assessed the Contribution that QM practices have on sustainability performance. The study was conducted in Vietnamese flower export firms. The sample size that was used in the analysis was 144. The study identified that QM has both a variable and positive impact on performance. It further identified that having constant improvement; ensuring the accuracy of data and proper presentation, organization support, and quality design promotes sustainability. The aspects of quality management focused on were accuracy of data and proper presentation, organization support, and quality design. Other aspects like project framework and project policy were left out hence examined in this study.

Chatterjee [41,4] investigated the relationship between management and evaluation of the project. The survey utilized primary data. The analysis was done through descriptive and inferential statistics. The finding indicated that evaluation aids in management by tracking project development and aiding indecision-making. The study also indicated that evaluation provides intercession with first indications of progress or failure in fulfilling project goals. The major gap from the study is that it focuses mainly on evaluation in relation to decision making as opposed to project sustainability which was the main focus in the current study.

Bluml, Brock, Hamstra, and Tonrey [42] studied the effect of project evaluation on the achievement of projects in the Japanese manufacturing sector. The study indicated that evaluation provides a comparison between actual results and the set plans. It facilitates the assessment of what was expected, what was done, and how it was achieved. It can take place when the project is at its formative stage, to refine the strategy or how the project functions. The study also noted that evaluation helps participants in coming up with decisions on what could aid in meeting the agreed goals. The main focus of the survey was the Japanese manufacturing company whose context is different from that of Kenya in that there are diverse regulations on projects across countries.

Batselier and Vanhoucke [19,2] investigated the effect that monitoring and evaluation impacts on private hospital projects. They utilized primary and secondary data. The analysis was performed by determining descriptive and inferential statistics. They established that stakeholder participation is important in fostering sustainability since: it offers learning opportunities that address the needs of those who are most affected; promotes ownership, empowers the major stakeholders, and enables corrective actions to be taken to enhance project results. Participation in monitoring and evaluation has substantially less significant if populace individuals and local partners have not been included much earlier in the project cycle. The major gap is that the evaluation management practices like strategic plans assessment and management intervention were left out hence the current study filled the gap.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

This is a visual outline of the association between the study variables. The graph depicts the relationship between the dependent and explanatory factors. This illustrates how the study's variables are affected or interact with one another in order to arrive at a valid conclusion. Stakeholder Needs Assessment, cost management, quality management and evaluation management were employed as explanatory variables for strategic management practices. The sustainability of projects of funded projects by WFP was the dependent variable, in accordance with the study's unique objectives. The conceptual framework is exhibited in the figure below.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher, 2021

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

It is an overall plan of the research Creswell & Creswell. [44] It is a technique that provides a structure through which the scholar collects and presents data. This study was descriptive. As Chatterjee [41,5] put it, a descriptive research design describes existing phenomena by investigating individual perceptions. It does so by responding to whom, what, and how questions about the variable Dannels. [45,1] This design is analytical and often singles out a particular matter and describes it in depth. It therefore helped in gaining information about the impact that project management practices have on the sustainability of the funded project in Nairobi, case of feeding program in schools. It assisted in evaluating the association between the variables; stakeholder needs assessment practices, cost management practices, quality management practices, and evaluation management practices of funded projects in Nairobi, case of feeding program in schools.

3.2 Data Collection Instruments

Structured questionnaire with both closed and open-ended questions were utilized to gather data. The questions touched on cost management, stakeholder analysis, quality management, and monitoring as well as evaluation of projects about sustainability. The questionnaire was divided into six sections. Section A presented the general and back ground information of the respondents, Section B contained statements on stakeholder needs assessment and practices, Section C, presented statements on project cost management practices, Section D presented statements on project quality practices, Section E contained statements on project monitoring and evaluation practices while Section F presented statements on project sustainability.

3.3 Data Analysis

A regression model determined the relationship between stake holder’s assessment, cost management, quality management, and monitoring as well as evaluation management on sustainability by showing the magnitude of the relationships Dannels. [45,2] The results of both descriptive and inferential analysis were summarized using tables. To achieve the four objectives, the multiple regression equation given below was estimated. The magnitude and the direction of the coefficient of each variable were interpreted accordingly. If the sign is positive, it indicates a positive relationship between dependent and independent variables and vice versa. If the coefficient is significant then the variable is important in explaining the change in the dependent variable. This was done after establishing that the adjusted R² is 50% and above.

The regression model adopted is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \epsilon \text{ -----(3.1)}$$

Where:

Y = Dependent variable herein known as Sustainability

X₁ = Stakeholder Needs Assessment practices

X₂ = Cost Management Practices

X₃ = Quality Management practices

X₄= Evaluation Management practices

β = constant,

β₁, β₂, β₃ and β₄= Regression Coefficients

ε = Error Term

3.4 Operationalization of Variables

Table 1: Operationalization of Variables

Variable	Defination	Scale of Mesurement	Expected Sign
X1=Stakeholder needs assessment practices	Stakeholder attribute	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Stake holder legitimacy	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Stakeholder communication	Likert Scale 1-5	Negative
X2= Cost management practices	Estimate project cost	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Project Budget	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Control project cost	Likert Scale 1-5	Negative
	Project framework	Likert Scale 1-5	Negative
	Management practices	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Project policy	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Management intervention	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
X3= Quality management practices	Strategic plans assessments	Likert Scale 1-5	Negative
	Objective assessments	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive

X4 = Evaluation managemnt practices	Reduced drop out	Likert Scale 1-5	Positve
	Completion rates	Likert Scale 1-5	Positive
	Innovitions techniques eg kitchen gardening	Likert Scale 1-5	Posive
	Improved performance	Likert Scale 1-5	Negative

Source: Researcher, 2021

Likert scale 1-5 (scale of 1-5 where: 1- Strongly disagrees, 2- Disagree, 3- not sure, 4- Agree, 5- Strongly agree)

4. DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Regression Analysis

A multiple regression analysis was done to determine the link between project management practices and project sustainability. This part exhibits the summary of the model and the regression coefficients.

The model summary helps in showing the coefficient of determination (R²) which explains the changes in the project sustainability due to changes in project management practices. The model summary is as shown in Table 4.13.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.834 ^a	.696	.687	.28497

a. Predictors: (Constant), Project Monitoring And Evaluation Management Practices, Project Cost Management Practices, Stakeholder Needs Assessment Practices, Project Quality Management Practices

Source: Field Data (2021)

According to the results in Table 4.13, the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.834 equivalent to 83.4%. The coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.696 which is equivalent to 69.6% while the adjusted R² is 0.687 which is 68.7%. As stated by Dannels, [45,3] the coefficient of determination is adjusted to eliminate any biases. Based on the findings it can be inferred that 68.7% of the changes in the project sustainability is explained by the project management practices used namely; stakeholder needs assessment, project cost management practices, project quality management practices and project monitoring and evaluation. It also implies that 31.3% of the changes in project sustainability is explained by other factors besides the project management practices.

4.2. Regression Coefficients

This was aimed at showing the relationship between project sustainability and project management practices. The regression coefficients are shown in Table 4.15.

Table 3: Regression Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.732	.227		3.231	.002	.284	1.180
	Stakeholder Needs Assessment Practices	.116	.067	.115	1.739	.084	-.016	.248
	Cost Management Practices	.433	.087	.501	4.957	.000	.260	.606
	Quality Management Practices	.190	.072	.201	2.628	.010	.047	.333
	Monitoring And Evaluation Management Practices	.467	.057	.563	8.220	.000	.354	.579

a. Dependent Variable: Project Sustainability

Source: Research Data (2021)

From the regression coefficients in Table 4.14, the model becomes;

$$Y = 0.732 + 0.116X_1 + 0.433X_2 + 0.190X_3 + 0.467X_4 + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y = Project Sustainability

X₁ = Stakeholder Needs Assessment practices

X₂ = Cost Management Practices

X₃ = Quality Management practices

X₄ = Evaluation Management practices

β = constant,

β₁, β₂, β₃ and β₄ = Regression Coefficients

ε = Error Term

From the outcome of the results presented in Table 4.14, a unit increase in the stakeholder needs assessment practices leads to an improvement in project sustainability by 0.116 times other variables kept at a constant. The improvement in project sustainability is not significant given that the p value is 0.084 which is >0.05. With a unit change in project cost management practices keeping the other variables constant, the project sustainability increases by 0.433. The increase is significant based on the p value of 0.000. Moreover, as the project quality management practices increases by a unit, the project sustainability improves by 0.190 times which is significant based on the p value of 0.010. With a unit improvement in project monitoring and evaluation practices, the sustainability of project is improved by 0.467 which is significant since the p value is 0.000.

4.3. Discussion of the Findings

From the outcome of the results presented in Table 4.14, a unit increase in the stakeholder needs assessment practices leads to an insignificant improvement in project sustainability by 0.116 times other variables kept at a constant. The findings reveal a positive relationship between stakeholder needs assessment practices and sustainability of the projects. A review of the previous studies reveals similar outcome. A study by Kamalirad et al. [46,1] which assessed how primary stakeholders' involvement through communication influence the outcome of complex projects. The findings reveal a positive relationship between stakeholder's communication and success of complex projects. In another assessment, Kamalirad et al. [46,2] established that stakeholder features impacted the organization's performance of a project. Dannels, [45,3] equally found that stakeholders have a lot of influence on project performance in the building industry.

With a unit change in project cost management practices keeping the other variables constant, the project sustainability increases by 0.433. The increase is significant based on the p value of 0.000. The outcomes concur with the outcomes from the past studies. For example, a study by Collings, Wood, and Szamosi, [39,2] while assessing on the impact of resource planning established that cost management is fundamental in the success of a project. In another study, Wolf and Floyd [47] found that cost management practices have an impact on the performance of businesses. Chatterjee [41,6] also revealed that cost management practices positively influence project performance.

Moreover, as the project quality management practices increases by a unit, the project sustainability increases by 0.190 times which is significant based on the p value of 0.010. A review from the previous studies shows that quality management has an effect on the new project development. Chatterjee [41,7] studied the impact of quality management on the development of new projects. The survey revealed a positive association between quality management practices and project sustainability. Dannels, [45,4] did a survey on the impact of total quality management on the project sustainability and established a positive significant relationship between the quality management practices and project sustainability. Bluml, Brock, Hamstra, and Tonrey [48,1] assessed the Contribution that QM practices have on sustainability performance and established a positive relationship.

With a unit improvement in project monitoring and evaluation practices, the sustainability of project is improved by 0.467 which is significant since the p value is 0.000. a review of a study by Dannels,[45,5] established that monitoring and evaluation exercises helps in improving project performance. A study by Galas, Morell, established that evaluation of projects helps in achieving an objective assessment of ongoing projects and this helps in determining the success and sustainability. Moreover, Bluml, Brock, Hamstra, and Tonrey [48,2] established that the project evaluation has a positive and significant impact on the success of projects in the Japanese manufacturing sector.

The theories utilized in the survey supports the findings. For instance, the theory of change is applicable in bringing maintainable advancement through quality control and cost the board. The theory of change applies to sustainable progress through quality control and cost control. This is because project implementers must strive for great results by applying these ideas well in the engagement cycle, in order to fabricate advanced educational speculations on change, to aid intercession that can be adjusted in unique circumstances. Therefore, the theory supports the findings on the significance of project quality practices.

The findings on the stakeholder needs assessment is reinforced by the empowerment theory proposed by Bluml, Brock, Hamstra, and Tonrey [48,3] which advocates for people's empowerment through participation and engagement with others. The theory is premised on the assumption that sustainability of a project can only be realized through engagements among people. Therefore, in project management sustainability can be ensured through stakeholder needs assessment as established in the findings.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The objective one was established the impact of stakeholder needs assessment practices on project sustainability. Based on the outcomes, the survey concludes that stakeholder needs assessment practices has an insignificant and positive effect on project sustainability since the coefficient is 0.116 times and p value is 0.084.

The objective two focused at exploring the effect of project cost management practices on project sustainability. From the outcomes, it can be concluded that project cost management practices have a significant and positive effect on the project sustainability as shown by coefficient of 0.433 and p value of 0.000.

The objective three was aimed at evaluating the effect of project quality management on project sustainability. From the findings, the survey remarks that project quality management has a significant and positive effect on the project sustainability since the coefficient is 0.190 and the p value is 0.010.

Lastly the study aimed at evaluating the effect of project monitoring and evaluation practices on project sustainability. From the results, it is concluded that project monitoring and evaluation practices, has a positive significant impact on the sustainability of project as illustrated by the coefficient of 0.467 and the p value of 0.000.

5.2. Recommendations

From the outcomes, the research concludes that stakeholder needs assessment practices has an insignificant and positive effect on project sustainability since the coefficient is 0.116 times and p value is 0.084. The survey recommends that the organizations should pay keen attention to project cost management practices especially the aspect of budgeting by ensuring that the budgets are realistic and reflect the actual cost of the projects. The variances should be continuously assessed and where there are significant variances, there has to be proper justification.

From the study results, it can be remarked that project cost management practices have a significant and positive effect on the project sustainability as presented by coefficient of 0.433 and p value of 0.000. The study thus recommends that project quality management practices should be enhanced through benchmarking and ensuring that they are ISO Certified. Benchmarking will help in understanding the standards that guides similar processes in project management. Through benchmarking the organization can also be able to do a SWOT analysis.

From the results it is concluded that project monitoring and evaluation practices, has a positive significant impact on the sustainability of project as shown by the coefficient of 0.467 and the p value of 0.000. Hence on the issue of monitoring and evaluation, the study recommends that a monitoring committee should be established to review the projects on regular basis for instance it can review the projects on daily basis to ensure that in case of any challenge, the challenge can be addressed in time.

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APPENDICES - A

APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE

The questions below are used to obtain information for academic use only. Kindly tick as appropriate.

Please complete the questionnaire below: -

SECTION A: GENERAL CHARACTERISTIC

1. Gender?

Female [] Male []

2. Indicate your level of education attained.

certificate [] Diploma [] Bachelor []

Master's Degree [] Others (Specify)

4. Number of years have you been working in the food programme?

Below 3 years [] 4- 6 years []

7- 10 years [] More than 10 years []

SECTION B: STAKEHOLDER NEEDS ASSESSMENT PRACTICES

The following are statements on the effect of Stakeholder needs assessment on sustainability. Signify your agreement level with these parameters utilizing a scale of 1-5 where: 5- SA, 4- D, 3- UD, 2- A, 1- SA

Table 4: Stakeholder needs assessment practices

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
We involve our stakeholder in our key decision making	☐				
Stakeholders policy are well integrated in our organization	☐				
Our stakeholders are given authority to work on behalf of the organization	☐				
We are affected by funding situations in our organization	☐				
We have adequate resources allocation in our organization	☐				
We have effective communication path for feedback	☐				
We have involved the beneficiaries in giving ideas about the feeding programme	☐				
We have adequate plans to ensure accountability in the feeding programme	☐				

SECTION C: PROJECT COST MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

The following are statements showing the effect of Project cost management on sustainability. Signify your agreement level with these parameters utilizing a scale of 1-5 where: 5- SA, 4- D, 3- UD, 2- A, 1- SA

Table 5: Project cost management practices

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
Every task touching the food project is well budget					
We have planning charts completed by breaking down every principle activity into a variety of tasks					
We have a cost control system for project activities in the ministry					
Individuals accountable for each task are specified					
We involve experts to project budgets for every programme					

SECTION D: PROJECT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

The following are statements showing the effect of Project quality management on sustainability. Signify your agreement level with these parameters utilizing a scale of 1-5 where: 5- SA, 4- D, 3- UD, 2- A, 1- SA

Table 6: Project quality management practices

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
We track class attendance for beneficiaries of feeding programme					
We have adequate policy to manage all programmes					
Our human resource management have adequate knowledge on employees need					
Our management provide support for new ideas					
We have adequate design to control data collection and reporting					

SECTION E: PROJECT MONITERING AND EVALUATION MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

The following are statements showing the effect of Project evaluation management on sustainability. Signify your agreement level with these parameters utilizing a scale of 1-5 where: 5- SA, 4- D, 3- UD, 2- A, 1- SA

Table 7: Project monitoring and evaluation management practices

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
We allow the community to participate in assessing project performance					
Lessons learnt from assessing projects have been implemented					
Participation of the community in monitoring and evaluation enhances performance of the food project in our organization					
The community has been made aware of the tools used in monitoring and evaluation					
There has been constant evaluation of the food project procedures and management					
The community has been involved in coming up with strategies to better performance of the food project					

SECTION F: PROJECT SUSTAINABILITY

Find herein statements on sustainability. Signify your agreement level with these parameters utilizing a scale of 1-5 where: 5- SA, 4- D, 3- UD, 2- A, 1- SA

Table 8: Project sustainability

Statement	1	2	3	4	5
We have adequate policy to ensure sustainability					
We are able to eradicate poverty and hunger					
We have adequately provided financial assistance to the community					
We have met the intended goals of the project.					